

SCHOOL HEALTH AND NUTRITION PROGRAM AMONG DEPED SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

This descriptive quantitative research design evaluated and determined the implementation of School Health and Nutrition Program of the 3 divisions of Surigao del Sur Province namely Surigao del Sur, Tandag City, and Bislig City for the 3 consecutive School Years : 2015-2016, 2016-2017, and 2017-2018.

Findings revealed that in the profile of the school respondents, most of the teachers were not Masteral and Doctoral Degree holders, while all school nurses are baccalaureate graduates with no Masteral or Doctoral degree units. Thirty nine percent (39 %) of the school heads are doctoral degree holder, 22% are masteral holder, and 39 % were not masters or doctors degree holder. However, regardless of the educational attainment they were able to implement school health and nutrition program in every respective school.

On the level of implementation of the school health and nutrition Program, findings revealed that all core component namely health and nutrition education, health and nutrition services, healthful school living and school-community coordination for health and nutrition are Well Implemented .

Likewise, there is no significant relationship between the profile of the school to the level of implementation of school health and nutrition program among the three (3) divisions in Surigao del Sur, Bislig City and Tandag City division respectively.

Moreover, *lack of health personnel* leads the problems encountered in the implementation of the school health and nutrition program with the adjectival description

of Serious (S). However, based on the over-all result, the problems encountered are Slightly Serious.

Keywords: *Health and Nutrition Program, Curricular Effectuality, PEACE Model*

INTRODUCTION

Health and nutrition are vital in the learning process. In the Philippines, nutrition and health in school is implemented through the School Health and Nutrition Program of the Department of Education. In Surigao del Sur division, both elementary and secondary schools are actively implementing and initiating several interventions to support and sustain the vision of the program in elevating the health and nutritional status of the learners and contribute to the quality of education by addressing fundamental health and nutrition needs that keep children out of school. Hence, this study intends to evaluate how the school implement the program as to its four core components in order to determine future policy intervention.

School health and nutrition program is a universal program that primarily deal with nutritional and health wellness of the children. It functions to guide and guard children in terms of their health, factors affecting their health, and ways of improving their health and skill to acquire more knowledge as they venture learning inside the school premise. (School Health and Nutrition Program Updates 2010). It is also an intervention that aim to improve the health and nutrition of school-age children, their related behaviors and skills, and consequently, their participation in school and education outcomes.

In the Philippines, Tabunda (2016) cited that the Department of Education (DepEd) in support to school health and nutrition program has been conducting a conditional food transfer program and health services to address malnutrition and poor health among learners. One strong feature of school health and nutrition programs is that they benefit the poor, sick, and hungry children far more than better-off children. Ruiz and Guiking (2013) revealed that in the four core components of the program only health and nutrition education was highly implemented while the other 3 core components all rated as implemented.

Though the program has been implemented for several years in the Department of Education, poor health and malnutrition among students remain the country's social problems which is the main reason for school absenteeism and dropouts (DO 49 s. 1997). Data also revealed that there are 158 students who are severely wasted and 964 are considered to be wasted in secondary schools, while in the elementary level there are 2,185 who are severely wasted and 7,569 wasted thus resulted to poor health and malnutrition remains a social problem the province. In addition, 14,886 children were found out to be below normal and an addition of 2,656 secondary students came out to be under nourished as well (Consolidated Report on Nutritional Status of secondary Students C.Y. 2017-2018).

These dilemmas encouraged the researcher to frame a proposed PEACE model in implementing the school health and nutrition program to the respondent schools of the three respondent divisions. This model shall guide the health implementers in implementing the school health and nutrition program in their respective schools. The

PEACE model is a sequential process to deliver an effective and efficient program. PEACE is an acronym that stands for P is for Plan , E is for execute , A is for analyze , C is for construct and E is for Evaluate.

Research Questions

1. What is the profile of the school respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 number of enrolment;
 - 1.2 total number of teachers;
 - 1.3 highest educational attainment of;
 - 1.3.1 teachers;
 - 1.3.2 school heads;
 - 1.3.3 school nurses; and
 - 1.4 health program?
2. What is the level of implementation of School Health and Nutrition program as perceived by the program implementers as to;
 - 2.1 health and nutrition education;
 - 2.2 health and nutrition services;
 - 2.3 healthful school living; and
 - 2.4 school-community coordination for health and nutrition?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the schools and the implementation of school Health and Nutrition Program?
4. What are the problems encountered in the implementation of School Health and Nutrition Program in public secondary schools?
5. What Intervention Program and Health and Nutrition Model can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed the descriptive quantitative research design to evaluate and determine the implementation of DepEd school health and nutrition programs in public secondary schools. In this method, the researcher collected, analyzed, described and examined data. And whatever it was, did not interfere with the situation, condition and variables and did not tamper or controls them.

Specifically, descriptive survey attempts to describe characteristics of subjects or phenomena, opinions, attitudes, preferences and perception of persons of interest to the researcher. Moreover, a descriptive survey aims at obtaining information from the representative of the population and from that sample; the researcher was able to present the findings as being representative of the population (Orodho, 2009). This descriptive evaluative design was applied in evaluating and determining the implementation of DepEd school health and nutrition programs.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in sixteen (16) public secondary schools of the three (3) Divisions namely: Tandag City Division, Surigao del Sur Division and Bislig City Division. The respondents schools were chosen from all public secondary school in their divisions through fishbowl technique. The respondents schools per division were chosen from the three categories: small, medium and big. Moreover, Respondents' schools from the three divisions were determined through fishbowl method.

Big schools are schools with above 1,000 students' population. For Surigao del Sur division it includes Cantilan National High School and Madrid National High School; for Tandag City division it includes Jacinto P. Elpa National High School; and for Bislig City division: Bislig City National High School and Tabon M. Estrella National High School.

Medium schools are schools with students' population of less than 1,000 but greater than 500. In this study medium schools were the following: For Surigao del Sur division Carmen National Agricultural High School and Parang National High School, for Tandag City division is Buenavista National High School, and for Bislig City division are Mangagoy National High School and Maharlika National High School.

Small schools are those with a population of less than 500 pupils. Union National High School and Agsam Integrated School were among of the small schools in Surigao del Sur division; for Tandag City are Vicente L. Pimentel Sr. National High School and Carmen Integrated School; and for Bislig City were Tumanan National High School and Bucto National High School.

Research Respondents

The study included 70 respondents: 23 secondary school heads/principals, 9 school nurses and 38 MAPEH teachers across the three divisions in the province of Surigao del Sur namely Surigao del Sur division, Bislig City division, and Tandag City division.

Research Instrument

This study adopted a standardized questionnaire of Ruiz & Guiking (2013) on the study entitled, "Strategies for optimizing implementation of the school health and Nutrition Program in Public Elementary Schools in the Philippines".

The instrument is made up of three (3) parts, namely: Part I will collate data on the profile of the school respondents; Part II will determine the level of schools' implementation of the DepEd School Health and Nutrition Program as to Health and Nutrition Education, Health and Nutrition Services, Healthful School Living and School-Community Coordination for Health and Nutrition. Part III is on the problems/challenges met in the implementation of DepEd school health and nutrition programs and practices and this part is made up of fourteen (14) statements designed to measure how serious are the challenges perceived by the respondents in three (3) divisions.

The responses to each item in the questionnaire under the level of implementation of the 4 core components of the School Health and Nutrition Program namely health and nutrition education, health and nutrition services, healthful school living, and school – community coordination for health and nutrition and the level of seriousness of the problems met in the implementation of the said program were tallied and computed. Its mean and standard deviation were taken and interpreted using the criteria set in the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

The following steps were followed by the researcher in the conduct of the study: Firstly, before the administration of the research instrument, the researcher secured permission for the conduct of this study from the Schools Division Superintendents of the three divisions namely Bislig City , Tandag City and Surigao del Sur. Along with it was the letter requesting the respondents namely the MAPEH teachers, school nurses, and school heads to answer sincerely the items indicated in the questionnaire. Secondly, the researcher personally distributed the survey questionnaire to the respective respondents to administer and facilitate the gathering of data. The researcher adapted a standardized questionnaire of Ruiz & Guiking (2013) on the study Strategies for optimizing implementation of the School Health and Nutrition Program in Public Elementary Schools in the Philippines. Thirdly , the researcher personally collected the survey questionnaire from the respondents .He then grouped the retrieved questionnaires by division, then tallied and tabulated , scored and classified the gathered data with the assistance of his statistician. Lastly, with the help of the statistician , the results were analyzed and interpreted based on the objective of the study as expressed in the sub-problem. After the inferences were formulated, a Model was designed to improve school health and academic outcomes of the students.

Statistical Treatment

In the analysis and treatment of data, the researcher used the following statistical tools to answer:

The researcher used simple frequency counting, percentage and raking for problem 1, Weighted Mean for the problem numbers 2 , and Chi Square for problem 3,. These tools determined the Implementation of School Health and Nutrition Program in three respondent divisions.

RESULTS

Table 1
Profile of Respondents by School

Classification of School	Name of Schools	Division	Enrolment	Number of Teacher	Highest Educational Attainment				SHNP Program	
					Category	Teachers	School Heads	School Nurses		
Small Schools	Union NHS	Surigao del Sur	117	10	Ph.D./ED.D	0			/	
					M.A.	0				
	Agsam NHS	Surigao del Sur	282	21	Bachelor	10	1		/	
					Ph.D.	0				
	Vicente L.Pimentel Sr. NHS	Tandag City	279	11	M.A.	1			/	
					Bachelor	20	1			
	Carmen Integrated School	Tandag City	264	8	Ph.D./ED.D	0			/	
					M.A.	0				
	Tumanan NHS	Bislig City	151	7	Bachelor	8	1		/	
					Ph.D./ED.D	0				
	Bucto NHS	Bislig City	163	13	M.A.	1			/	
					Bachelor	6	1			
Medium Schools	Camenl NAHS	Surigao del Sur	503	24	Ph.D./ED.D	0			/	
					M.A.	4				
	Parang NHS	Surigao del Sur	548	21	Bachelor	20		1	/	
					Ph.D./ED.D	0				
	Buenavista NHS	Tandag City	782	28	M.A.	2			/	
					Bachelor	19	1			
	Mangagoy NHS	Bislig City	611	26	Ph.D.	0	1		/	
					M.A.	2				
	Maharlika NHS	Bislig City	545	24	Bachelor	28	1	1	/	
					Ph.D./ED.D	1	1			
	Big Schools	Cantilan NHS	Surigao del Sur	2186	58	M.A.	2			/
						Bachelor	23		1	
Madrid NHS		Surigao del Sur	1836	65	Ph.D./ED.D	0	1		/	
					M.A.	5	1			
Jacinto P. Elpa NHS		Tandag City	3554	128	Bachelor	60		1	/	
					Ph.D./ED.D	4	1			
Bislig City NHS		Bislig City	1602	54	M.A.	9	1		/	
					Bachelor	115	1	1		
Tabon MENHS		Bislig City	1821	99	Ph.D./ED.D	2	1		/	
					M.A.	7				
						Bachelor	45		1	/
						Ph.D./ED.D	2	1		
Total			15,244	597		608	23	9		

Table 2

Health and Nutrition Education

Indicators	Schools			Average Weighted Mean	Adjectival Description
	TANDAG	SDS	BISLIG		
1 Teachers integrate basic health and nutrition concepts in the curriculum.	4.50	4.08	4.14	4.24	Very Well Implemented
2 Teachers conduct health and nutrition lectures/talks to classes or students before and after any health activity.	4.75	4.00	4.18	4.31	Very Well Implemented
3 Health personnel conduct in-service trainings and seminars for teachers on current health and nutrition problems.	4.13	3.62	4.11	3.95	Well Implemented
4 Health personnel conduct health and nutrition guidance and counseling to students.	4.31	3.88	4.07	4.09	Well Implemented
5 Health personnel confer with the teachers about the kind of follow-up needed by the students.	4.44	4.12	3.93	4.16	Well Implemented
6 Health personnel act as resource person to strengthen health and nutrition program implementation.	4.63	3.77	4.14	4.18	Well Implemented
Over-all average weighted mean				4.16	Well Implemented

Table 3

Health and Nutrition Services

Indicators	Schools			Average Weighted Mean	Adjectival Description
	TANDAG	SDS	BISLIG		
1 Health personnel perform physical assessment (examination of the eyes, ears, nose, throat, neck, mouth, skin, <u>extremities</u> , posture, heart and lungs.)	4.06	3.46	4.04	3.85	Well Implemented
2 Health personnel conduct height and weight measurement (procedure of evaluating the nutrition status of the students).	4.88	4.58	4.46	4.64	Very Well Implemented
3 Health personnel determine the physical and mental fitness of the pupils who will participate in physical education <u>programs</u> , athletic meets and other related activities.	4.69	4.04	4.11	4.28	Very Well Implemented
4 Health personnel provide feeding program to qualified beneficiaries.	4.81	3.92	4.36	4.36	Very Well Implemented
5 Health personnel perform oral examination, oral prophylaxis.	4.06	3.38	3.75	3.73	Well Implemented
6 Teacher conducts classroom inspection (<u>fast</u> inspection of students in the classroom noting their general cleanliness, signs and symptoms of illness and treatment or correction made.)	3.56	3.50	4.04	3.70	Well Implemented

Table 4

Healthful School Living

	Indicator	Schools			Average Weighted Mean	Adjectival Description
		TANDAG	SDS	BISLIG		
1	Classrooms adequately ventilated and lighted.	4.56	4.23	4.11	4.30	Very Well Implemented
2	Functional clinic is set up.	4.44	3.35	3.71	3.83	Well Implemented
3	Maintenance of a school canteen.	4.75	3.88	4.04	4.22	Very Well Implemented
4	Adequate potable water supply for drinking and handwashing/food washing.	4.63	3.85	3.82	4.10	Well Implemented
5	Availability of tooth brushing facilities.	4.25	3.12	3.61	3.66	Well Implemented
6	Proper waste disposal.	4.75	3.35	4.00	4.03	Well Implemented
7	Toilet bowls and urinals sufficient for the students.	4.25	3.46	3.57	3.76	Well Implemented
8	Playground safe and free from hazard.	4.31	4.04	3.82	4.06	Well Implemented
9	Fire prevention equipment.	4.13	3.81	4.14	4.03	Well Implemented
10	Adequate provision and maintenance of school health facilities.	4.19	3.35	3.86	3.80	Well Implemented
Over-all average weighted mean					3.98	Well Implemented

Table 5

School- Community Coordination for Health and Nutrition

	Indicator	Schools			Average Weighted Mean	Adjectival Description
		TANDAG	SDS	BISLIG		
1	Parents are invited to attend P.T.A meeting to discuss health and nutrition issues and needs.	4.13	4.04	3.96	4.04	Well Implemented
2	Health personnel confers with parents/teachers concerning health status and needs of children.	4.25	3.65	4.04	3.98	Well Implemented
3	Health personnel follow-up cases of sick <u>children</u> , teachers and other school personnel through house/hospital visits .	4.06	3.38	3.89	3.78	Well Implemented
4	Health personnel coordinate with community health agencies regarding proper management and referrals and other health and nutrition projects.	4.38	3.54	4.07	4.00	Well Implemented
5	Parents and other people in the community participate in health survey to discover health and nutrition needs and problems.	3.88	3.58	3.89	3.78	Well Implemented
6	Join civic action activities in cooperation with <u>professional</u> , civic and religious organizations , local government units and DOH.	4.19	3.85	4.07	4.04	Well Implemented
Over-all average weighted mean					3.94	Well Implemented

Table 6

Significant Relationship between the Profile and Level of Implementation of School Health and Nutrition Program

School Profile	Implementation of SHNP	Computed (X ²)	Tabular value @ 5%	Conclusion	Decision
Enrolment	3.96	1.78	12.60	Accept	Not significant
Number of teachers		4.40	12.60	Accept	Not significant
HEA of Teachers		8.42	9.49	Accept	Not significant
HEA School Heads		1.48	9.49	Accept	Not significant
HEA of School Nurses		0	9.49	Accept	Not significant

Table 7

Problems Encountered in the Implementation of School Health and Nutrition Program

	Problems	Schools			Average Weighted Mean	Adjectival Description
		Tandag	SDS	Bislig		
1	Lack of knowledge and skills on how to integrate health concepts.	2.13	2.27	1.79	2.06	SS
2	Lack of support from school administrator.	2.06	1.54	1.71	1.77	NS
3	Lack of time of teachers in supervising the health activities of students.	2.31	1.92	1.89	2.04	SS
4	Lack of coordination between parents and teachers	2.00	1.81	2.04	1.95	SS
5	Limited number of school children is benefited by health and nutrition services.	2.38	2.08	1.96	2.14	SS
6	Lack of improvement observed in the home, school, and community.	2.50	2.46	2.18	2.38	SS
7	Lack of parents support to the health and nutrition services	2.69	2.38	2.18	2.42	SS
8	Lack of training knowledge on the different components of the program	2.38	2.27	2.21	2.29	SS
9	Lack of support from the community.	2.50	2.19	2.14	2.28	SS
10	Tolerance of some teachers of poor health habits and practices.	2.25	2.04	2.14	2.14	SS
11	Lack of updated health and nutrition education materials.	2.44	1.81	2.31	2.19	SS
12	Lack of income generating project that will support health and nutrition activities.	2.63	2.62	2.14	2.46	SS
13	Lack of resources and funds for health and nutrition activities.	2.63	2.38	2.18	2.40	SS
14	Lack of health personnel	2.63	2.46	3.29	2.79	S
Over-all average weighted mean					2.24	SS

DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 depicts the profile of school respondents as to enrolment, number of teachers, highest educational attainment of Teachers, School Nurses, School heads and the implementation of school health and nutrition program (SHNP).

As reflected on the table, with regard to classifications of schools, small schools in three (3) divisions are Union National High School, Agsam Integrated School, Vicente L. Pimentel Sr. National High School, Carmen Integrated School, Tumanan National High School and Bucto National High School. Carmen National Agricultural High School, Parang National High School, Buenavista National High School, Mangagoy National High School and Maharlika National High School comprised the medium schools. Big schools include Cantilan National High School, Madrid National High School, Jacinto P. Elpa National High School, Bislig City National High School and Tabon M. Estrella National High School.

As to the enrolment, Union National High School of Surigao del Sur division has the lowest number of enrolment, 117, while Jacinto P Elpa National High School of Tandag City division ranked 1st as to highest number of enrolment, 3554. The overall enrollment across the 3 respondent divisions is 15,244. Ochada and Empes (2018) emphasized that enrolment is very important to consider in educational aspect because it is the basis of the allocation of the School Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE). This implies that the school with higher enrolment will receive a bigger amount of MOOE likewise the lower is the enrolment the smaller is the allocation. MOOE is the school budget downloaded from the government to all public schools for the utilization of running school operations.

With regard to the number of teachers, Tumanan National High School has the least number of teachers, 7, while Jacinto P. Elpa National High School has the highest number which is 128 teachers. The overall number of teachers in the 3 respondent divisions is 597. This implies that the greater number of teachers in the school, the more implementers of the program wherein the program will be given emphasis and focus since there are designated in charge / focal person to manage. And this would positively affect in the implementation of school health and nutrition program in the school.

According to Samudara (2011) teacher plays a very significant role in students' curricular achievement, when teachers are effective classroom managers, their students achieve at a higher level. Ronfeldt (2015) added that teachers do make a tangible difference in student achievement. Vermunt (2014) further verified that high quality teacher learning influences student-learning outcome as a result.

As to educational qualification of teachers and school heads it can be gleaned from the table that the division of Bislig City has the highest number of teachers with doctorate degree followed by Tandag City division then Surigao del Sur division. For school heads, Surigao del Sur ranked 1st. then Bislig City division then Tandag City division. This implies that school heads and teachers who are doctors degree are more updated in managerial, leadership, and program implementation since they are keeping themselves abreast with the new trends by pursuing doctoral degree. This further implies that the government

should provide an avenue such as granting scholarship for doctors degree for school heads and teachers where they can update their selves to become globally competitive.

According to Ladd & Sorensen, (2015) teachers who earn their advanced degrees show a deep level of understanding and commitment to the profession, allowing them to modify curriculum goals and programs , adjust teaching methods, and enter leadership positions to enact the system-wide changes in education. Advanced degree programs give teachers insight into the theoretical and practical backgrounds that drive their professions, learning how knowledge of education theory positively impacts their teaching practices. By applying theory to teaching methods, teachers gain the benefit of seeing their students excel in the classroom.

As to educational qualification of school nurses, all respondent-nurses are Baccalaureate degree holder. It is further revealed on the table that all respondent small-schools don't have school nurses. The health program of the said schools are implemented through school district nurses who are stationed at the district office and who has been visiting once a week to all small schools. This simply implies that the fraction number of school health implementers is not enough in accommodating the growing number of children in school . And therefore, allocation of addition school nurse item could be a prime consideration by the government to have a smooth and effectual implementation of the program.

As cited in Pediatrics (2013) that the school should have school nurse to facilitate the implementation of the program in the school and to render health services among learners. They are responsible in providing intervention to students health problems to augment students normal development in physical and intellectual aspects. They collaborate also with community. And as a community partner their role is to inform parents on the health of their children and capacitate parents on healthy parenthood . On the otherhand, having advance degree for nursing simply means increasing understanding. An MSN will allow to build on the knowledge during undergraduate years and cultivate a deeper understanding of the medical profession and area of specialty. With enhanced knowledge a school nurse feel more confident in his/her work knowing that he/she provides his/her very best care (Graduate Guide 2016) .

As to the practices of School Health and Nutrition Program, key informants revealed the varied practices and initiatives in their respective schools. Key informant 1 said that she was initiating school-based feeding program dubbed as Project GRACE (Growth and Radiance through Aided and Caring Efficacies) where fund for the said program was taken from the different sources such as donations from sponsored teachers, non-teaching personnel and other external stakeholders. She also monitored the height and weight status of the students regularly to determine their nutritional status. She also added the following practices: closely monitored the teachers' blood pressure, oral examination among students, and gave first aid seminars to students.

Key informant 2 shared some practices in their school and these are the following: initiated 15 minutes Zumba dance every morning after flag ceremony, sponsored poster making contest during nutrition month in their school and invite RHU physician to do a check-up of their students and teachers regularly.

Key informant 3 enumerated the following practices: hand washing before and after recess and lunch time , simultaneous toothbrushing among Grade 7 students before

first period in the afternoon , invited eye specialist once a year for vision check up among students and teachers, and regular feeding program.

According to Shaw (2015) health and nutrition practices must be incorporated into daily living and must be practiced all the time and later these practices will evolve into culture. This only means that health and nutrition must be a priority and a consideration anytime and anywhere. This is to promote the overall health, hygiene and nutrition among students. Health and nutrition practices vary from school to school to suit on the needs of the learners as health and nutrition are concerned . These school practices however provide the opportunities to every learner to grasp the importance of a healthy well being.

Level of Implementation of School Health and Nutrition Program as perceived by the program implementers as to Health and Nutrition Education.

The implementation of School Health and Nutrition Program of the respondent-schools in the three divisions in this study is discussed thoroughly in the succeeding tables in terms of its indicators and categories. Weighted mean was utilized in the discussion of every data presented in the tables.

From the table, it can be gleaned that the indicator 3 health personnel conduct inservice training and seminar for teachers on current health and nutrition program has the lowest weighted mean of 3.95 (Well Implemented) while the indicator 2 teachers conduct health and nutrition lectures/talk to classes or students before and after any health activity leads on the list with the average mean of 4.31(Very Well Implemented).

The result simply shows the alertness and readiness of teachers in sharing their potential to students on health and nutrition matter to make them realized the importance of health and nutrition and to keep them fit and healthy.

The result relates with study of National Centers for Education Statistics (2010) that teachers are important in the delivery of nutrition education to accomplish three important objectives. The first is to convey needed information, or the facts about nutrition, so students are knowledgeable about healthy eating practices. The second is to change unhealthy attitudes so students have the motivation to establish healthy eating practices. The third is to teach positive skills so students have all the tools to accomplish their nutritional goals.

Level of implementation of School Health and Nutrition program as perceived by the program implementers as to Health and Nutrition Services

It can be gleaned on the table 3 that domain number 2 which states that Health personnel conduct height and weight measurement rank 1st (Very Well Implemented) with the weighted mean of 4.64. While domain (Availability of School Dentist) got the lowest average weighted mean of 1.37 (Not Implemented) which talked on the availability of school dentist in school.

Furthermore, the over-all average weighted mean of 3.73 with the adjectival description of Well Implemented only proved that the school nurses and the teachers of the three divisions performed well. However , it is the big challenge among the three divisions on the availability of school physician and school dentist in the school.

The result implies that some students with tooth-related and health-related problems could not be accommodated/treated right away with the absence of school

dentist and school physician. Some schools' initiatives would be initiated to address the problem.

Moreover, the result also implies that the government should look into some possibilities of providing school dentist and school physician to schools or district to take charge of the total health and nutrition among learners. Indeed, the school is the place where health care and nutrition is a priority and primarily needed among children.

The findings conformed with Basic Education Statistics (DepEd 2011) that in the Department of Education there was a big gap in terms of school health manpower in the country. The DepEd physician-to-student-ratio is 1:120,936 public school pupils. This situation occurs because most Health and Nutrition Sections (HNSs) have only one medical doctor while some even have none. The dentist-to-student-ratio is 1:25,487 while the nurse to student ratio is 1:5,537. A nutritionist-dietitian is employed only in the Regional level. Putting this into perspective that a school year in the Philippines is only about nine and-a-half months long, there is really a dearth of health personnel in DepEd.

Level of implementation of School Health and Nutrition program as perceived by the program implementers as to Healthful School Living

On the Healthful School Living of table 4, it reveals that indicator 5 *availability of tooth brushing facilities* got the lowest average weighted mean of 3.66 (Well Implemented) while the indicator 1 *classroom adequately ventilated and lighted* rank 1st with the average weighted mean of 4.22 (Very Well Implemented) .

The result implies that the school has adequate, functional, and well-maintained school physical facilities which are essentially needed by the children to have a healthy body and better learning experience. This further implies that the government shall have a financial allocation in sustaining the physical facilities of the school .

Antor & Awu (2018) explained the impact of the physical school environment .Accordingly ,it has a strong influence on the health of children. It protects students and staff against immediate injury or disease and promotes prevention activities and attitudes against known risk factors that might lead to future disease or disability.

Moreover , Marx and Wooly (2013) support that a school environment that is well maintained with safe and clean facilities will naturally attract students more; it will promote their health and glue them to their studies which in turn will boost academic achievement.

Level of implementation of School Health and Nutrition program as perceived by the program implementers as to School-Community Coordination for Health and Nutrition

It can be clearly gleaned on table 5 that there are two domains got the top rank with the Average weighted mean of 4.04 (Well Implemented). These are Parents are invited to attend P.T.A meeting to discuss health and nutrition issues and needs and Join civic action activities in cooperation with professional , civic and religious organizations , local government units and DOH . Meanwhile, two domains also got the bottom rank with the average weighted mean of 3.78 (Well Implemented). These are Health personnel follow-up cases of sick children , teachers and other school personnel through house/hospital visits and Parents and other people in the community participate in health survey to discover health and nutrition needs and problems”.

The result implies that external stakeholders such as parents and community serve as effective partner in the delivery of effective and efficient implementation of the program that surely affect the performance of their children. Moreover, it also implies that the school health implementers will initiate more activities to encourage more participation of the parents and become engaged in school activities.

This is supported by Llamas & Tuazon (2016) who emphasized the benefits of parental participation in the school. Accordingly, in terms of academic achievement the students greatly benefited from parental involvement. In addition it also helps in developing self-awareness, positive behavior, and improved personal characteristics as a whole. Parents also exposed working with other parents , teachers , and other stakeholder where they developed skills in establishing academic environment for their children. Moreover , the teachers are also benefited from parents' participation . Their ability in dealing with parents will be honed, speaking ability will be developed , and their relationship with parents will be strengthened.

Significant Relationship between the Profile of the Schools and the Implementation of School Health and Nutrition Programs

Table 6 emphasized the significant relationship between the profile of schools and the level of implementation of School Health and Nutrition Program. Details of the table are appended for further information on this component of the study.

As reflected on the table 8 , since the computed value of 1.78 on the profile for enrolment is less than its tabular value, 12.60 at .05 level, the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, the number of enrolment has no significant relationship to the successful implementation of school health and nutrition program.

It is also shown on the table on the school profile that the computed value for number of enrolment is 4.40 which is less than the tabular value of 12.60 at .05 level. Hence, it is evident that there is no correlation of the number of teachers to the successful implementation of the school health and nutrition program thus accepting the null hypothesis.

For the Highest Educational Attainment of teachers, nurses, and school heads, still there is no significant relationship to the successful implementation of the school health and nutrition program since the computed value is less than the tabulated value thus the null hypothesis is accepted.

This result implies that educational attainment whether baccalaureate, masteral, or doctoral attainment of teachers, nurses, and school heads is not the prime contributory factor in the successful implementation of school health and nutrition program.

Problems Encountered in the Implementation of School Health and Nutrition Program

Table 7 emphasized the problems encountered in the implementation of School Health and Nutrition Program. The data are reflected on the following table .

Table 9 presents the problems encountered in the implementation of School Health and Nutrition Program of the three divisions. As seen on the table, domain number 14 which is the lack of health personnel tops the problems encountered in the implementation of the program.

It has the average weighted mean of 2.79 which has the adjectival description of Serious (S) while the domain lack of support from administrator got the lowest average weighted mean of 1.77 (Not Serious).

The result implies that the school administrator , as stewards in education has utilized their full initiative in implementing the school health and nutrition program for the sake of the learners and teachers in the absence of school health personnel. It further implies that the Department of Education is in need of health personnel specifically the school physician and school dentist as lead implementers of the health and nutrition program in the school.

The result of the study is congruent to the study of Ruiz & Guiking (2013) that the lack of health personnel is very big challenge to the Division of Cadiz City since there is no dentist and medical doctor available in the schools and health section of the said division where in fact health personnel are front runners as health and nutrition is concerned.

Model Development

The result of the present investigation paved the way for a Proposed PEACE model in implementing the school health and nutrition program to the respondent schools of the three respondent divisions . The PEACE model is a sequential process to deliver an effective and efficient program. PEACE is an acronym that stands for P is for Plan , E is for execute , A is for analyze , C is for construct and E is for Evaluate.

Plan. This is the planning stage. The school will have a plan of the process of carrying out the objectives of the program. The planning includes the funding, facilities and equipments, policies and procedure, and organizational structure.

Execute. This is the action/application stage .In executing the plan one should have focus, commitment and passion on getting the goal. Sharp focus will clearly define pathways to success while commitment and passion create connectedness from oneself to the goal. Execute what is being planned. Follow all the details and act accordingly.

Analyze. This is a why-how stage. At this phase, analysis of why and how something happened takes place. Some activities here might succeed while others failed. Analyze the situation and think for the reasons for failure.

Construct. This is an implementation and intervention stage. Implement some interventions/alternatives for the failed activities in a carefully planned manner. This implementation of interventions/alternatives help in the realization of the objectives of the program.

Evaluate. This is the assessment phase. Evaluation of the program demonstrates the program success and progress .It also helps determine areas for improvement and ultimately help realize goals more efficiently.

Moreover, the model reflects 4 core components in the implementation of the school health and nutrition program. These are health and nutrition education health and nutrition services, healthful school living , and school-community coordination for health and nutrition.

The first core component is Health and Nutrition Education. This refers to the core component that cascade and disseminate information about health and nutrition to students and teachers. The role of the teachers here is to integrate and conduct lectures

on basic health and nutrition concept in the curriculum while the school nurse and other health personnel conduct some inservice person on the implementation of the program.

Health and Nutrition Services is the second core component of School Health and Nutrition Program that appraise , protect, and promote health and nutrition.It includes services on preventing illness by promoting sanitary conditions , access to emergency care for injury and nutrition services.Health personnel here will perform physical assessment,height and weight measurement, oral examination, provide feeding program while teacher conducts classroom inspection, familiarize students with simple first aid procedure, render first aid in case of emergency.

The third core component is Healthful School Living.This focuses on healthy and safe school environment where students have freedom of learning.It includes adequate ventilation and lighting of classrooms , functional health clinic, maintenance of school canteen, adequate potable water for drinking,handwashing and food washing, tooth brushing facilities, proper waste disposal, sufficient toilet bowls and urinals for students , safe playground, fire prevention equipments, and adequate provision and maintenance of school health facilities.

Lastly, the forth core component is School – Community Coordination for Health and Nutrition.This refers to partnership of school and community towards a healthy and well nourish learners. This includes attendance of parents in PTA meeting to discuss health and nutrition issues and needs, health personnel confers with parents/teachers concerning health status and needs of children, health personnel follow-up cases of sick children , teachers and other school personnel through house/hospital visits, health personnel coordinate with community health agencies regarding proper management and referrals and other health and nutrition projects, Parents and other people in the community participate in health survey to discover health and nutrition needs and problems, and join civic action activities in cooperation with professional , civic and religious organizations , local government units and DOH.

All of the above mentioned components of the a PEACE Model if given preferential attention,enough time, adequate or sufficient budget could lead to effectual and efficient School Health and Nutrition Program implementation .

This PEACE model is capsulized through a schema in figure 1.

Fig 1. PEACE Model for Effectual and Efficient SHNP Implementation

Proposed Intervention Plan

The PEACE intervention is a designed intervention to strengthen the implementation of the school health and nutrition program among Deped secondary schools.

Proposed Action Plan

Plan, Execute , Analyze, Construct, Evaluate (PEACE) Intervention

I. Rationale and Description

PEACE intervention is an intervention plan designed to help the school health implementers in implementing the school health and nutrition program in their respective school. The plan involves gaps identification, objectives, proposed strategies or activities to be undertaken in order to address the identified challenges or gaps. The person’s involved, budgetary requirements, for the different activities including the fund source, time frame or duration for each activity as well as the expected outcomes are likewise included in this plan. PEACE is an acronym which stands for P-plan, E-execute, A-analyze, C-construct, and E-evaluate.

II. Objectives:

PEACE Intervention aimed to:

1. identify the problems or challenges encountered by the schools health implementers in implementing the school health and nutrition program;
2. construct an action plan , strategies or activities to address the identified challenges or gaps;
3. propose the focal persons for the activities and allocate funds needed for these activities; and
4. promote the culture of excellence among health implementers in implementing the program
implementing the program

III. Action Plan

Gap	Objective	Strategies / Activities	Time Frame	Persons Involved	Budgetary Requirement	Source of Fund	Expected Output
Lack of school health personnel : physician and school dentist	Acquire Item for school health personnel:	PLAN: Formulate Plan of action on acquiring school physician and school dentist Item per district	January – March 2019	Division Superintendent, Education program supervisor, District Supervisor	P500	MOOE/Local funds	Action Plan
		EXECUTE: Enumerate the possible ways/strategies of acquiring school health physician and school dentist per district	January – March 2019	Division Superintendent, Education program supervisor, District Supervisor	P500	MOOE/Local funds	Enumerated possible ways/strategies of acquiring items
		ANALYSIS: Determine the best way of acquiring item for school physician and school dentist per district through SWOT analysis	January – March 2019	Division Superintendent, Education program supervisor, District Supervisor	P500	MOOE/Local funds	Identified the best way/strategy in acquiring Item
		CONSTRUCT: Implement the best way/strategy of acquiring school physician and school dentist per district	April 2019	Division Superintendent, Education program supervisor, District Supervisor	P5,000	MOOE/Local funds	Implemented the best way/strategy in acquiring item
		EVALUATE: Determine the number of Items for	May 2019	DepEd, DBM, Division Superintendent,	P500	MOOE/Local funds	Acquired Items for school health personnel:

	physician, and school dentist	school physician and school dentist		Division			physician, and school dentist
Lack of income generating project that will support health and nutrition activities	Generate Fund through Income Generating Project to support health and nutrition activities	PLAN: Formulate plan of action in determining the possible sources of income generating project	June-August 2019	School heads, school health personnel, teachers, PTA	P500	Local Fund, GPTA Fund	Action Plan
		EXECUTE: Determine the possible sources of IGP	June-August 2019	School heads, school health personnel, teachers, PTA	P500	Local Fund, GPTA Fund	Enumerated possible sources of IGP
		ANALYZE: Determine the best IGP through SWOT Analysis	June-August 2019	School heads, school health personnel, teachers, PTA	P500	Local Fund, GPTA Fund	Identified best IGP
		CONSTRUCT: Implementation of the best Income Generating Project	June-August 2019	School heads, school health personnel, teachers, PTA	P5000	Local Fund, GPTA Fund	Implemented the best IGP
		EVALUATE: Assess implemented IGP as to the feasibility in Fund raising	June-August 2019	School heads, school health personnel, teachers, PTA	P500	Local Fund, GPTA Fund	Generated Fund to support health and nutrition activities
Lack of parents support to the health and nutrition services	Increase parents support to the health and nutrition services	PLAN: Make a plan of activities in maximizing the parents' support to SHNP	June-August 2019	School heads, school health personnel, teachers, PTA	P500	GPTA Fund	Activity Plan
		EXECUTE: Enumerate some activities that maximize the parents support to health and nutrition services	June-August 2019	School heads, school health personnel, teachers, PTA	P500	GPTA Fund	Enumerated activities
		ANALYSIS: Determine the most effective activity in maximizing the parents support to health and nutrition services	June-August 2019	School heads, school health personnel, teachers, PTA	P500	GPTA Fund	Identified most effective activity that maximizes parents' support to health and nutrition services

		through SWOT Analysis					
		CONSTRUCT: Implement the best activity in maximizing the parents support to health and nutrition services	Monthly	School heads, school health personnel, teachers, PTA	P10,000	GPTA Fund	Implemented the most effective activity
		EVALUATE: Evaluate the activity through the number of parents' attendance	Monthly	School heads, school health personnel, teachers, PTA	P500	GPTA Fund	Increased parents support to the health and nutrition services
TOTAL					P25,500		

Conclusions

Respondent teachers, school nurses, and school heads show competence and boundless knowledge in the implementation of the school health and nutrition program despite of being an undergraduate of masters and doctors degree, still they were able to implement the program successfully with the adjectival value of Well Implemented.

All core components of school health and nutrition program were given greater emphasis by teachers, school nurses, and school heads during the implementation.

Having graduate studies such as masters degree and doctors degree is not the absolute assurance in a successful implementation of the school health and nutrition program.

Moreover, the unavailability of school physician and dentist in school is really evident but it does not serve as total barrier in the implementation of the program.

Recommendations

Teachers, school nurses, and school heads should pursue post baccalaureate degree such as masters and doctors and attend trainings on health and nutrition to update new trends, techniques, ideas, and the use of modern technology in dealing with nutrition and health issues thus to improve more on the implementation of the said program in their respective schools. In addition, School heads, school nurses, and teachers may likewise attend refresher course or attend leadership seminar on the conduct of the said program to enrich their managerial skills for a better nutrition and health services.

Sustainability plan on the program specifically on the four core components may be provided to have adequate and appropriate health and nutrition care among learners.

Regular evaluation and monitoring of the program may be given priority to determine some related concerns and issues on the program's implementation.

The Department of Education must give preferential attention and look into possibilities of providing school physician and school dentist as stewards of total health and nutrition state among learners and mentors.

Future researchers are likewise inspired to conduct similar exploration on the implementation of the said program. This is to provide possibilities of entertaining some issues not probed in this research.

School health implementers such as teachers, school nurse, and school head may utilize the PEACE model and the PEACE intervention plan in their respective school for effectual and efficient program implementation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher conducted the study by taking the following steps: first, the researcher obtained permission from the Schools Division Superintendents of the three divisions, namely Bislig City, Tandag City, and Surigao del Sur, to conduct the study before administering the research instrument. It was accompanied by a letter asking the respondents—MAPEH teachers, school nurses, and school administrators—to provide honest responses to the questionnaire's questions. Second, in order to oversee and expedite the collection of data, the researcher personally gave the survey questionnaire to each individual respondent. The researcher adopted a standardized questionnaire of Ruiz & Guiking (2013) on the study Strategies for optimizing implementation of the School Health and Nutrition Program in Public Elementary Schools in the Philippines. Thirdly, the researcher personally collected the survey questionnaires from the respondents. With the help of his statistician, he then divided and sorted the retrieved questionnaires before tallying, tabulating, scoring, and classifying the data. Finally, the data were examined and interpreted using the statistician's assistance, taking into account the sub-problem's stated study purpose. Following the formulation of the conclusions, a model was created to enhance learners academic performance and school wellness

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